

Task 52 general meeting 2025

LiDAR in complex terrain

LiDAR Task: Complex terrain working group

- **About**

- The complex terrain working group of IEA wind LiDAR Task 52 focuses on the application of ground based (vertical profiling) wind LiDAR in complex terrain and/or complex flow.

- **Aim**

- The uncertainties involved with LIDAR measurements in “complex terrain” are one of the main obstacles to a more widespread application of wind LIDAR. As there is no clear method or metric to identify complex terrain, this uncertainty affect the acceptance of LiDAR measurements in general.
- Task 52's complex terrain working group focuses on the following questions:
 - Quantification of the “complexity” of a site in a meaningful way with regard to ground-based LIDAR measurements.
 - Identification of thresholds (in some suitable measure for complexity) for the application of ground-based LiDAR (for an accepted measurement uncertainty).
 - Prediction of terrain-induced measurement errors as a function of terrain complexity.
 - Suitable techniques to compute corrections for the effect of the complexity and the remaining uncertainty in the LIDAR data after the application of a correction.

The problem:

- Measurement of the beam-axis component only:

$$u_{\text{measured}} = \frac{u_{1\parallel} - u_{2\parallel}}{2 \cdot \sin \alpha}$$

- Different wind speeds with different flow geometries give same measurement result.

$$u_{\text{measured}} = \frac{u_{1\parallel} - u_{2\parallel}}{2 \cdot \sin \alpha}$$

- Different wind speeds with different flow geometries give same measurement result.

$$u_{\text{measured}} = \frac{u_{1||} - u_{2||}}{2 \cdot \sin \alpha}$$

Typical deviation between LiDAR and met-mast in complex terrain

Task 52's complex terrain data study

- In collaboration with LoTar (Martin Hofsäß)
- Verification study for ground based LiDAR in complex terrain.
- Robust guidance on the applicability of ground based LiDAR has to come from real-world data. Thus, the complex terrain working group attempted to assemble a broad and diverse database of parallel and co-located LiDAR and met mast data.
- To minimize concerns regarding data-confidentiality, the analysis has been done by distribution of data analysis tools rather than by distribution of data.
- Correlation with numerical measures describing terrain complexity should then give guidance on the applicability of ground based LiDAR in complex terrain, and, ideally, allow a prediction of the uncertainties involved with such measurements.
- The deliverable to this activity is scheduled to be a guideline to the application of ground based wind LiDAR in complex terrain.

Tool for terrain characterization

```

# Parameter file for terrain evaluation script
#
# by Martin Hofsaess, 2024-02-07
#
# Usage:
# ...-- Fill this text file, rename if you wish to do so.
# ...-- Paths can be either given as absolute or relative paths. White spaces are allowed.
# ...-- Open command window ("CMD")
# ...-- Navigate to folder containing the executable ("main.exe")
# ...-- Launch executable by typing, e.g.: "main.exe config.yaml"
#

# General informations about the project
general:
  project: test.xy .....# Specify a name for the site (white space allowed),
  savepath: C:\IEA52\ .....# Specify path for the analysis (use "." for local folder)

datapath:
  dgm : C:\DTM\N001E010.tif .....# Path to the DTM file to be used. If the path is empty, SRTM satellite data will be downloaded.
  srtm: D:\Projekte\srtm .....# Path where the downloaded SRTM-Data will be saved (use "." for local folder, white spaces are allowed, folder will be created when not existing)

# Specify met-mast information
mm:
  location:
    long: -115.21545032554769 .....# Longitude (x-coordinate) of met-mast position (use point as decimal separator)
    lat: 39.91467684181843 .....# Latitude (y-coordinate) of met-mast position (use point as decimal separator)
    source: 'EPSG:4326' .....# Coordinate system (https://epsg.io/) for the interpretation of met-mast long & lat

# Specify LiDAR information
lidar:
  location:
    long: -115.21555032554769 .....# Longitude (x-coordinate) of lidar position (use point as decimal separator)
    lat: 39.91468684181843 .....# Latitude (y-coordinate) of lidar position (use point as decimal separator)
    source: 'EPSG:4326' .....# Coordinate system (https://epsg.io/) for the interpretation of LiDAR long & lat

# Input
calcprop:
  parameter:
    reference: 100.0 .....# "reference" height; height at which the evaluation is taken place, usually measurement height of met-mast data

```

- The terrain evaluation program is provided as a windows executable file. The required input information, namely the coordinates of the site, the digital terrain model to be used, and the reference height for the analysis, are specified in an parameter text file.

Tool for LiDAR and met-mast comparison

The script for comparing LiDAR and met mast time series is provided as an Excel sheet containing Visual Basic (VBA) code. This also contains a sheet to document site properties and the technical particulars of the LiDAR and the met mast measurements.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	
	TimeStamp Met Mast	Wind Direction Met Mast [deg]	Mean Wind Speed Met Mast [deg]	TimeStamp LiDAR	Wind Direction LiDAR [deg] (height 1)	Mean Wind Speed LiDAR [m/s] (height 1)	(optional) Wind Direction LiDAR2 [deg] at additional height (height 2)	[m/s] at additional height (height 2)	Intensity Met Mast [1]	Intensity LiDAR [1] (height 1)	Intensity LiDAR [1] (height 2)	LiDARH2 [1] at additional height (height 2)	LiDAR [m/s] positive for updraft (height 1)	[m/s] at additional height (height 2)									
1																							
2	01.01.2000 00:00:00	151	4,7	01.01.2000 00:00:00	140,9	4,48	140,5	4,46	0,1702	0,2991													
3	01.01.2000 00:10:00	167	4,8	01.01.2000 00:10:00	156,5	4,93	155,9	4,95	0,1667	0,2049													
4	01.01.2000 00:20:00	167	4,8	01.01.2000 00:20:00	156,5	4,93	155,9	4,95	0,1667	0,2049													
5	01.01.2000 00:30:00	167	4,8	01.01.2000 00:30:00	156,5	4,93	155,9	4,95	0,1667	0,2049													
6	01.01.2000 00:40:00	167	4,8	01.01.2000 00:40:00	156,5	4,93	155,9	4,95	0,1667	0,2049													
7	01.01.2000 00:50:00	167	4,8	01.01.2000 00:50:00	156,5	4,93	155,9	4,95	0,1667	0,2049													
8	01.01.2000 01:00:00	167	4,8	01.01.2000 01:00:00	156,5	4,93	155,9	4,95	0,1667	0,2049													
9	01.01.2000 01:10:00	167	4,8	01.01.2000 01:10:00	156,5	4,93	155,9	4,95	0,1667	0,2049													
10	01.01.2000 01:20:00	167	4,8	01.01.2000 01:20:00	156,5	4,93	155,9	4,95	0,1667	0,2049													
11	01.01.2000 01:30:00	167	4,8	01.01.2000 01:30:00	156,5	4,93	155,9	4,95	0,1667	0,2049													
12	01.01.2000 01:40:00	167	4,8	01.01.2000 01:40:00	156,5	4,93	155,9	4,95	0,1667	0,2049													
13	01.01.2000 01:50:00	167	4,8	01.01.2000 01:50:00	156,5	4,93	155,9	4,95	0,1667	0,2049													
14	01.01.2000 02:00:00	167	4,8	01.01.2000 02:00:00	156,5	4,93	155,9	4,95	0,1667	0,2049													
15	01.01.2000 02:10:00	167	4,8	01.01.2000 02:10:00	156,5	4,93	155,9	4,95	0,1667	0,2049													
16	01.01.2000 02:20:00	144	5	01.01.2000 02:20:00	139,9	5,02	139,8	5	0,1	0,1673	0,168	-0,32	-0,32										
17	01.01.2000 02:30:00	129	5,1	01.01.2000 02:30:00	126,9	5,07	127,2	5,09	0,1569	0,1519	0,1513	-0,18	-0,18										
18	01.01.2000 02:40:00	124	5,6	01.01.2000 02:40:00	120,6	5,44	120,8	5,48	0,1429	0,1746	0,1807	0,08	0,08										
19	01.01.2000 02:50:00	127	5,7	01.01.2000 02:50:00	125,4	5,66	125,5	5,72	0,1404	0,1731	0,1766	-0,13	-0,13										
20	01.01.2000 03:00:00	132	6,6	01.01.2000 03:00:00	129,4	6,67	129,1	6,79	0,0909	0,1124	0,1075	-0,08	-0,08										
21	01.01.2000 03:10:00	136	7,3	01.01.2000 03:10:00	130,7	7,17	130,7	7,33	0,0822	0,0907	0,0846	-0,15	-0,15										
22	01.01.2000 03:20:00	138	7,9	01.01.2000 03:20:00	134,4	7,75	134,1	7,9	0,0759	0,0787	0,0785	-0,16	-0,16										
23	01.01.2000 03:30:00	135	7,9	01.01.2000 03:30:00	131,5	7,92	131,9	8,01	0,0759	0,0821	0,0799	-0,08	-0,08										
24	01.01.2000 03:40:00	131	8,4	01.01.2000 03:40:00	126,7	8,2	127,2	8,41	0,0714	0,072	0,0713	-0,09	-0,09										
25	01.01.2000 03:50:00	132	8,8	01.01.2000 03:50:00	129,3	8,64	129,7	8,84	0,0795	0,0822	0,0814	-0,1	-0,1										
26	01.01.2000 04:00:00	141	8,8	01.01.2000 04:00:00	137,2	8,66	137,8	8,94	0,0795	0,0751	0,0761	-0,07	-0,07										
27	01.01.2000 04:10:00	150	9	01.01.2000 04:10:00	145,6	8,87	145,4	9,22	0,0778	0,0755	0,0694	-0,2	-0,2										
28	01.01.2000 04:20:00	222	17,4	01.01.2000 04:20:00	222,2	17,35	222	17,61	0,2566	0,2386	0,2351	-0,22	-0,22										
29	01.01.2000 04:30:00	249	16	01.01.2000 04:30:00	239,8	15,66	239,9	15,99	0,1813	0,1922	0,1876	0,06	0,06										
30	01.01.2000 04:40:00	256	13,2	01.01.2000 04:40:00	246,9	13,27	246,8	13,56	0,0985	0,1183	0,1158	0,13	0,13										
31	01.01.2000 04:50:00	253	10,7	01.01.2000 04:50:00	243,8	10,69	243,9	10,93	0,1028	0,1141	0,1208	0,16	0,16										
32	01.01.2000 05:00:00	249	7,4	01.01.2000 05:00:00	239,5	7,49	240,4	7,69	0,0946	0,0921	0,0962	-0,11	-0,11										
33	01.01.2000 05:10:00	277	6,1	01.01.2000 05:10:00	266,5	5,96	266	6,05	0,1475	0,1628	0,1636	0,04	0,04										
34	01.01.2000 05:20:00	273	4,3	01.01.2000 05:20:00	264,8	4,34	264,2	4,5	0,2326	0,2857	0,2867	-0,22	-0,22										
35	01.01.2000 05:30:00	263	9,2	01.01.2000 05:30:00	255	9,22	254,3	9,55	0,1087	0,1128	0,1037	-0,12	-0,12										
36																							
37																							
38																							
39																							
40																							
41																							
42																							
43																							
44																							
45																							
46																							
47																							
48																							
49																							

LiDAR height 1: [m] 100,7
 LiDAR height 2: [m] *<-- specify when 2nd LiDAR height is ticked above*

Magnetic declination [deg] 3,78 *<-- (Default is 0) link to calculation tool with correct sign. Magnetic declination*

Specify met-mast time stamp format

Example of time stamp 01.01.2000 00:00:00 *(copied from first line)*

Year YYYY
 Month MM
 Day DD
 Hour hh
 Minute mm
 Your Timestamp Syntax DD.MM.YYYY hh:mm:ss *<-- define time stamp format using definitions from the above lines, which is*

city coordinates and time zone for calculation of sun's eleva

Longitude 16,3331
 Latitude 48,88745
 Offset to UTC (time zone [h]) 1,00 *<-- e.g. +1 for central Europe (UTC+1), +2 when time stamps are in CEST (L*

Start calculation

How to use this Excel:

- 1) Enable macros. (you can have a look at the source code with Alt+F11)
- 2) Make sure that the decimal separator of your data and the one Excel uses are the same. (you can determine the latter by using the button "Check Excel separator")
- 3) Paste your data as plain text into columns A to F (G - M are optional). In particular, the time stamp data must be entered as text string, not in a genuine Excel time format! Correct alignment of time series is up to you! Data cleanup and filtering for LiDAR availability have to be done beforehand. (the data in the first 30 lines)

Task 52's complex terrain data study

- Received data from eight different participants in the working group Including Siemens Gamesa and Wind Pioneers (India).
- Overall 83 datasets from ~50 sites

Data analysis

- There is a systematic variation of mean wind speed error and of the stochastic errors with wind direction.
- Any description of these errors should thus also differentiate with wind direction (i.e. no integral measure)
- Focusing here on best candidates and experience from previous Task 32 activity.

Correlation with Li/MM error

	bin TSI acc. to 61400-1 [°]	bin TVI acc. to 61400-1 [%]	bin curvature (1D-method) [1/m]	bin curvature (2D-method) [1/m]	Range in elevation (p95-p5) [m]
1H	0,17	-0,18	0,33	0,33	-0,21
2H	0,22	-0,18	0,35	0,35	-0,22
3H	0,31	-0,25	0,38	0,37	-0,25
5H	0,37	-0,24	0,42	0,41	-0,31
10H	0,33	-0,25	0,40	0,40	-0,30

Correlation with interquartile range

	bin TSI acc. to 61400-1 [°]	bin TVI acc. to 61400-1 [%]	bin curvature (1D-method) [1/m]	bin curvature (2D-method) [1/m]	Range in elevation (p95-p5) [m]
1H	0,00	0,00	-0,06	-0,06	0,01
2H	-0,05	0,06	-0,08	-0,07	0,05
3H	-0,07	0,07	-0,09	-0,09	0,08
5H	-0,08	0,10	-0,10	-0,10	0,10
10H	-0,09	0,20	-0,09	-0,08	0,13

Corelation: 0.42

R ... curvature radius of the flow
 z ... measurement height

$$\frac{u_{LiDAR}}{u_{true}} = 1 - \frac{z}{R}$$

R_{Ter} ... curvature radius of the terrain with $R \approx R_{Ter} + z$

$$\frac{u_{LiDAR}}{u_{true}} - 1 = \frac{-z}{R_{Ter} + z}$$

Additional scaling-factor depending on the evaluation length, e.g. 0.6 for 5H

$$\frac{u_{LiDAR}}{u_{true}} - 1 = 0.6 \frac{-z}{R_{Ter} + z}$$

Corelation: 0.48

Subsequent analysis
done for 5H, similar
for other evaluation
lengths

- Stochastic error is almost unchanged between simple and complex terrain.

Red: distance
between Lidar and
metmast $> H_{\text{Ref}}$

Red: Forested sites

Red: high TSI values

Red: $H_{Ref} < 80m$

Red: $H_{Ref} < 45m$

Red: less than 50
points per bin

Red: participant A

Red: participant B

Red: participant C

Red: participant D

Red: participant E

Red: participant F

Red: participant G

Red: participant H

Time series analysis:

Solar elevation
as a proxy for atmospheric stability

LiDAR TI

Inflow angle

- Stochastic error is almost unchanged between simple and complex terrain.
- Systematic effect of terrain curvature on wind speed measured by LiDAR (for 5H)

$$\frac{u_{LiDAR}}{u_{true}} - 1 = 0.6 \frac{-z}{R_{Ter} + z}$$
- Data basis seems sufficiently large
- There are imperfect and/or peculiar sites, though overall the dataset is consistent
- What's next?

Thanks for your attention!

CONTACT:

Dr. **Alexander Stökl**

Energiewerkstatt Verein

 Heiligenstatt 23, 5211 Friedburg/Austria

 alexander.stoekl@energiewerkstatt.org

 +43 664 54 024 66

 +43 7746 282 12 - 26

 www.energiewerkstatt.org